

Research Software in an Age of AI-Assisted Development: Reflections from Edinburgh

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1. Introduction

Important: *This document began as a draft vision statement prepared in advance of the “[Research Software Engineering in the Age of Generative AI](#)” workshop, March 2026. It was intended to lead to discussion in the document before and discussion in-person at the workshop, including disagreement, and refinement. The current version of the document is a snapshot of that draft vision statement and some of the discussion. It captures a sense of the identified principles, benefits, challenges, and open questions, rather than having a single point of view that represents all of the workshop attendees and contributors. Not all authors necessarily agree with all the points in the document.*

A note on terminology: We use AI-assisted software development throughout this document to refer to tools and practices often described as Generative AI, GenAI, LLM-enabled development, or AI-assisted coding. We chose this term because it focuses on the activity we care about here, namely the production, verification, documentation, and maintenance of research software, rather than on a particular technology label or marketing category.

Research software, the source code, scripts, computational workflows, and infrastructure that power modern research, have never been more central to human discovery. And the scholarly community (funders, publishers, societies, etc.) increasingly recognizes this, though there is still a long way to go before such recognition is widespread or leads to systemic change.

At the same time, in the last few years, the rise of AI-assisted tools, i.e., those that can generate code and documentation by using large language and multimodal trained models, and act in semi-autonomous “agentic modes,” has caused significant disruption in software creation and society at large. These tools raise legitimate questions about training data provenance, licensing, quality, security, attribution, environmental cost, and accountability that are hard to ignore. Yet the conversation around AI-assisted tools too often seems to oscillate between hype and dystopian predictions. Neither of these extremes serve research well. This document also starts from the assumption that these tools are and will continue to be used, regardless of the concerns raised above, and aims to guide further usage within this context.

This document outlines some ideas about how research software can and *should* be produced in the era of AI-assisted research tools by Research Software Engineers, computational researchers, and domain experts writing their own code. It focuses on the software production function: building and maintaining software that meaningfully advances research, but also includes the people involved. Workshop participants discussed both, including the role of RSEs and how it will change, such as leveraging the ADSA/USE-RSE-led [Position Statement on Generative AI in the RSE Workplace](#) and related work in this space.

We believe that developing a shared vision of the future of research software is urgent: AI tools act as an amplifier of existing practices at every level: individual coding habits, institutional incentives, and the commercial priorities of the companies building these tools – accelerating whatever patterns they encounter, both good and bad. Applied without thought, AI-assisted tools

can proliferate bugs, embed and reinforce biases, and generate plausible-looking results faster than our existing systems of peer review and verification can check and absorb them. Applied with care and discipline, it has the potential to expand access to computational methods from those with software development skills to those without them, at least for those who can afford it, and allow all researchers to focus on the work that most requires human skill and judgment.

1.1. Definitions

- **Research software:** Borrowing from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5504016>, we define Research Software as source code files, algorithms, scripts, computational workflows and executables that were created during the research process or for a research purpose. We contrast this with software components (e.g., operating systems, libraries, dependencies, packages, scripts, etc.) that are used for research but were not created during or with a clear research intent, which should be considered software in research and not Research Software. (We note that this differentiation may vary between disciplines. In addition, there is much software that was not developed for research or used in research, which is also being affected by AI, in some cases similarly to research software and in some cases differently.) Research software can exist anywhere in the stack from applications and packages directly used by researchers to lower in the stack and including dependencies on which user-facing software is built (e.g., see <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2019.2900945>).
- **Research software engineering:** Software engineering is defined in IEEE Std. 610.12-1990 Glossary of Software Engineering Terminology and ISO/IEC/IEEE Systems and Software Engineering Vocabulary (SEVOCAB) as "the application of a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation, and maintenance of software; that is, the application of engineering to software." Research software engineering is therefore "the application of a systematic, disciplined, quantifiable approach to the development, operation, and maintenance of research software; that is, the application of engineering to research software."
- **Research software engineer:** A research software engineer is a person who has the role and/or career of research software engineering. Research software engineers typically have expertise in software engineering and understanding and experience of research, and are able to apply software engineering as appropriate for a research area.
- **Researcher:** In the context of research software engineering, a researcher is a person who is attempting to solve a scholarly problem, often through the use of research software. This research software may be developed and maintained by a research software engineer who works in collaboration with the researcher.

1.2. Potential benefits of AI-assisted research tools

As much of this document will focus on risks and challenges, it's important to start with some of the potential benefits. Potential AI benefits include that it could:

- Enable more and faster experimentation; help researchers fail quicker and not waste limited resources (including RSEs) on ideas that will not work
- Help people understand code better, when they might never have bothered before (however, many tools and platforms are not currently optimized for this case). e.g., to find and explain errors in code, and explain to researchers how code is working, potentially leading to code reuse
- Improve documentation by automating routine parts of it, allowing people to focus their time on the parts of documentation that require more human attention.
- Improve testing, perhaps dramatically; testing is often a weakness in research software today, so there is the potential for significant gains here
- Multiply what a single RSE can do (note that many RSEs do not work collaboratively with other RSEs) by enabling single, trained RSEs to tackle bigger and more complex projects because they can focus on the highly-skilled work and use AI-assisted tools for the other parts
- Help with maintenance through increased automated scans for vulnerabilities and the ability to suggest and apply fixes; a lot of research code today never gets reviewed again by humans
- Make some research possible that wasn't before, e.g., by reducing development time, generating scenarios or responsive AI characters for social science work, processing data in new ways, increasing accuracy of automated processing methods
- Run automated reproducibility reviews for research software via agentic models that can assess whether the code matches the methodology that it runs, and that the published results are retrievable

2. Principles

The ultimate measure of the value of research software is the knowledge and progress it enables.

While many of us take great pride in authoring high-quality, well-designed code, we do not create research software for its own sake. Ultimately we write software to advance humanity's understanding and to improve the world around us. One view of software has been that it is the understanding we have of research encoded in actionable form, just like papers have been the knowledge in literary form. Whether that's modeling complex systems, analyzing vast datasets, or running experiments that test theories against observations, our software exists in service of discovery and societal progress.

AI-assisted tools are rapidly changing who can create code, and allow them to do so at rates faster than any human has historically been able to. This shift in code production is worthless unless the software produces results we can trust or verify.

Our vision of the future of research software production rests on the following key principles:

2.1. The pursuit of knowledge is a human responsibility

AI can assist with a broad range of activities, including generating code, identifying patterns, and automating routine tasks. The essential questions of research – what is worth studying, how to interpret results, what the findings mean – are fundamentally human. The responsibility for research integrity cannot be delegated to a machine with no understanding of truth, no capacity for ethical judgment, and no way to be meaningfully held to account for its choices. Human agency and accountability must remain at every key decision point.

2.2. Engineering discipline is more important than ever

When every researcher is equipped with a tool that can generate code faster than humans can review it, the bottleneck shifts from code production to verifying the resulting system's behavior. And verification becomes more demanding: when humans write code, their domain knowledge implicitly prevents certain classes of errors. AI-generated code carries no such guarantees. This is true for all research software, from one-off analysis scripts to shared open-source community tools to application software, all of which might be used by a single researcher, a community, or many communities, to investigate a research question, enable the investigation of multiple research questions, or apply previously captured knowledge.

What engineering “discipline” looks like depends on context: For shared open-source tools, we have established practices of testing, code review, version control, and documentation. For quick, AI-assisted tasks, the equivalent is likely lighter but still necessary: checking outputs against expected behaviour, testing edge cases, not assuming the code is correct merely because it runs. The specifics will vary, but the principle is the same: if you can't check that it works, you shouldn't trust the results.

Open questions: How is coding via prompt the same as programming at a higher level of abstraction than previous, such as going from assembler to compiled languages? How much understanding is needed of the internals of what is generated, vs just the functionality? This ties to testing as well, where testing could be considered white box, gray box, or black box. Which is needed in which situations?

Discussion: Many of the software quality challenges that AI amplifies already exist. Many researchers write code that is untested or not sufficiently tested. And very few RSEs always apply best practices (for any definition of best practices) in the world of research creation.

Discussion: The use of AI-assisted tools could lead to individuals who feel less responsible for the code and its output: a researcher may feel more personally invested in the accuracy of code they have written. And they are inherently more capable of assessing its accuracy through code review if they were capable of writing it in the first place. But they are just as responsible for AI-generated code as they were for code they wrote from scratch. Testing and verification becomes even more important than it was before. TDD (test driven development), where tests are initially created to reflect the end goal of a "prompt request" and then the code is produced to create a closed loop of agentic code generation should be considered.

Open question: What skills and ways of thinking does effective use of AI for research software actually require, given that prompting is not simply "programming at a higher level of abstraction" but introduces fundamental differences around precision, determinism, reproducibility, and the relationship between intent and implementation?

Discussion: 1) Programming has had a one-to-one correspondence between abstraction and its expansion; the precision of expression remained in all abstractions. This is lost in prompt engineering. It is much easier to introduce wrong behavior through underspecification because natural languages are by nature imprecise. AI coding is probabilistic, while the other one is deterministic. 2) We can't meaningfully say we've taught someone programming skills unless we've equipped them with the ability to do something repeatable, which requires consistent / predictable output from the same input. And for projects worked on by multiple people in collaboration, source code exists in part as a shared human readable representation of the system; it needs to be both readable enough for humans to reason about and specific enough to produce repeatable results during execution, natural language prompts don't do those things. 3) In many cases, prompting is merely the constructing of a more elaborate search query. In other cases, it may be the high-level or alternate-mode description of a desired system. Yet in other cases, it may be a replacement for a CLI command. This also depends on the "mode" of the tool at hand (e.g., "Ask", "Plan", "Agent" modes).

2.3. Transparency and reproducibility remain mission-critical

Research is iterative and builds on prior work. As more researchers work with AI agents operating semi-autonomously, the risk grows that we collectively produce ever-increasing volumes of results while losing track of how they were produced, or that we know how they were produced but that errors happened along the way.

This matters for two reasons: First, research builds in a sequence of dependent activities and if something is wrong at one step, everything downstream may be affected. Tracing errors requires knowing not just what was done, but how each step connected to the next. Second, AI shifts work to a higher level of abstraction from explicitly writing code to prompting an AI for code. This creates a gap between intent and implementation with the AI producing implementation choices the user didn't explicitly specify, and the basis for those choices not

being visible in the final output. The code exists, but the reasoning that connected the researcher's goals to that particular implementation may not.

AI-assisted tools can accelerate research, but it can just as easily mass-produce findings that appear credible but do not hold up to scrutiny. With these new abstractions and a gap between intent and implementation, capturing not just research provenance, but the reasoning and decisions that shaped the outcomes are no longer a nice-to-have; these activities are now essential for a research enterprise that needs to verify its own work.

This challenge is not entirely new. Researchers have faced similar transparency problems before, for example when using GUI-based statistical tools that produce results without a durable record of the steps taken to generate them. The research community has made progress in recognising why this practice is problematic and in advocating for scripted, reproducible, and versioned workflows, in order to increase transparency. AI-assistance risks reintroducing the same problem in a new form: generating results through interactions that may not be captured, preserved, or reproducible. The lesson from that earlier experience applies here too: if the process isn't recorded in a form others can inspect and rerun, the results are harder to trust, though AI also introduces additional challenges through its probabilistic (non-deterministic) nature.

Transparency is a longstanding issue in research, and to some extent, in research software. AI assistance adds a new layer of complexity because prompting moves programming to a higher level of abstraction, disclosing that AI was used is not enough. We need norms for documenting the decisions and constraints that shaped the output, along with the prompts and models that were used, to ensure that future researchers can understand what was done and why. This may mean that the artifacts we expect for reproducibility need to expand e.g., specifications and requirements used to generate code, not just the code itself.

Open questions: Does this “prompting gap” between intent and implementation pose an additional risk to reproducibility? Is this genuinely new? Why might this be different from historical/earlier abstractions? Is human-readability of code still important? And what level of understanding is actually needed: when is black-box testing (“it produces correct outputs”) sufficient, and when do we need to understand the internals? How do we ensure accountability when code creators may not understand the code they produce?

Discussion re the prompting gap: Getting researchers to define what they are doing more precisely, to think more clearly about their problem/question, is already a challenge. There is frequently a gap between what someone says they are researching and what their research can actually tell them. Today, if you ask an RSE to create software with poorly defined instructions, they have a role and responsibility to ask questions, make reasonable decisions, use the R part of their RSE title, etc. A researcher working directly with an AI system today doesn't have this check from their RSE partner/collaborator because today's AI tools have sycophantic tendencies and a bias towards producing something. But they could potentially be structured to seek input/verification, identify assumptions, etc. Coding assistants could be more neutral in

their interaction, perhaps first planning and ensuring that the plan matched the researcher's needs, and that the researcher understands the plan and the code.

Discussion re human-readability: A lot of how we define well-written code is based on code being first and foremost written for humans. Does this remain a top priority? Is human-readable code still important? Do we also need to consider how to make code more interpretable by machines?

Discussion re black box testing vs having internal knowledge: This is not really new in the RSE community; it's also been an existing question before AI-assisted tools. RSEs sometimes are engaged in an engineering effort (building a tool of some sort) and other times in a knowledge creation effort (trying to understand how things work -- or more specifically, have worked in the past). This also is related to the partnership that can exist between RSEs and researchers, where in a tightly coupled collaboration, both parties might be involved in both internal understanding and external testing, and in a looser one, the researcher may take on the role of the external testing. In both cases, however, some level of external testing is always essential, as in much of science and engineering, where the design of an experiment or analysis typically involves an estimate of the results before the experiment or analysis is run, as a first step towards ensuring that it is working. Some new questions also arise, e.g., how should testing practices change to catch errors that human developers would implicitly avoid, and what role can approaches like TDD and/or spec-driven development play in capturing intent before code generation?

2.4. Software engineering is a function, not just a role

As AI-assisted tools lower barriers to code generation, we should expect more researchers to engage directly in software development. This is an exciting opportunity – but only if the expansion of those who produce code comes with a corresponding expansion of those who understand how to leverage these tools in order to create maintainable, well-focused, correct software.

In principle, ensuring that research software is correct, maintainable, and reproducible is the responsibility of everyone who writes code in service of research, yet historically the knowledge and practices needed to achieve this have resided mostly with software specialists. This leads to a situation where research software is of highly variable quality that is often correlated with the software engineering skills of its developers. AI makes it easier to develop more code, but not necessarily higher quality code.

This shift changes the role of these software specialists: Research software engineers increasingly become not just the people who can write software, but the people who can ensure that software is written well – through code review, mentorship, infrastructure design, and the cultivation of engineering culture across research teams. As AI handles more routine development tasks, RSEs may also shift toward more complex infrastructure work and toward shaping the AI-assisted tools and agents that others use to create software. Best practices must

become the accepted norm for everyone who produces code: domain scientists using AI-assistance for analysis scripts, dedicated engineers building shared infrastructure, and everyone in between. And the need for this function as an essential part of research software must be better understood and better supported.

Open questions: What competencies should be expected of people who use AI tools to create research software? What education and training is needed for this?

Discussion: The role of an RSE has been and in the age of AI will continue to be more than just producing code. RSEs have additional technical and non-technical skills: they are technical experts who can help a researcher understand software and hardware architectures and options, and by communicating and interacting with researchers, they can help them define what they want to implement and what is possible.

Open questions: How might the evolving RSE role in an AI era affect the attractiveness and sustainability of the profession? How do we balance the interests of current and future RSEs with what the research enterprise needs going forward?

2.5. Sustainability requires investment in people

Research software often outlives the grants that fund it and the careers of the people who initially built it. Sustainable research infrastructure requires institutional commitment, community maintenance, and ongoing investment in human expertise. AI-assistance can accelerate certain tasks, but it cannot replace the human relationships, institutional knowledge, and long-term stewardship that sustainable software requires.

This is especially true for the collaborative, trust-building work that turns individual tools into shared infrastructure. AIs cannot negotiate between competing requirements, build human consensus around standards, or mentor the next generation of research software practitioners. These remain human responsibilities.

Open questions: Who should be responsible for developing best practices for the different parts of this (deciding between requirements, developing standards, mentoring and training). Options include researchers who develop software, research software engineers, and researchers who study software engineering. What can we learn from how industry has approached similar challenges around long-term maintenance, knowledge transfer, and sustainability?

3. Key risks

Erosion of critical skills: If AI-assistance becomes a shortcut around understanding, our collective capacity for critical evaluation will degrade. We may produce more code while understanding less of it. And if today's well-trained software experts (e.g., RSEs) can only work effectively on building and testing software using AI-assistance because of the knowledge they gained before these tools existed, how will the next generation of software experts learn the same skills?

Open questions: Is understanding AI-generated code actually necessary, or is effective testing sufficient? (E.g., the UK's research integrity framework requires that you understand what you have done and why, but does that understanding need to be of the code's functionality or of the details within the code?) If understanding the lines of code matters, who needs it – the researcher, the RSE, someone else? And do our testing practices need to change e.g., more integration testing (black-box) and less unit testing (white-box)? What can we learn from historical practices here (e.g., the paradigms of testing when software was on floppy disks and shipped in shrink-wrapped boxes? Is there something to learn here from testing ML models where the provenance is sometimes unclear?

Note: Additional effects on people also may be discovered over time, potentially affecting individual general wellbeing in the workplace or outside it.

Reproducibility at scale: The non-deterministic nature of current AI tools, combined with rapidly evolving models and unclear provenance, threatens the reproducibility that underpins science. As with all research software, what matters is that we maintain a sufficient record of what was done.

Quality at scale: The ease of generating large quantities of code quickly means that without sufficient investment in review and validation, AI-generated volume may amplify bugs and propagate subtle errors throughout research. As with all research software, what matters is that the behaviour of the resulting software is well understood and verifiable.

Perverse incentives: Existing incentive structures in the scholarly system already reward speed and quantity of outputs over their quality and reliability. AI does not change these incentives but risks pushing them to a breaking point by dramatically increasing the volume of production without a corresponding increase in quality. The danger is that the signal of genuine research advances is drowned out by noise, slowing the incorporation of new knowledge and eroding public trust in research at a time when that trust is already fragile.

Ethical questions: LLMs have often been trained on code scraped without regard to licensing or consent. Beyond training data, unresolved questions remain about attribution, authorship, and accountability. Who is responsible when AI-generated code produces flawed results or introduces new security vulnerabilities? How should credit be assigned? The research community won't be able to defer these questions indefinitely. And both the research software

community and the larger software community also need to determine issues around copyright that AI systems may ignore.

Open questions: What ethical obligations do researchers have when using AI-assisted tools trained on code of uncertain provenance? Should the research community develop guidance on tool selection, attribution practices, or accountability for AI-assisted work?

Institutional misunderstanding: Decision-makers may see AI-assisted tools as an opportunity to reduce investment in human software expertise. The need for skilled practitioners who can evaluate AI outputs and maintain long-term infrastructure is increasing, not decreasing. This is especially true for early career developers: if we do not invest in building their skills, we will not have the experienced practitioners of tomorrow who are needed to use AI tools effectively and responsibly.

Widening gaps: Access to advanced AI tools varies widely across institutions, disciplines, and geographies. Without deliberate attention, AI-assisted tools could exacerbate existing inequities in computational research capacity, concentrating advantages among the already well-resourced. Alternatively, it could close gaps by reducing the knowledge required to generate software, or it could widen gaps by giving an advantage to people who know AI well (or have time to develop such knowledge) over those who don't.

Discussion: AI today has specific costs (subscriptions, compute, API usage). Training people in research software development and maintenance also has costs, but these costs are more varied across different global regions, leading to potentially different decisions on relative value. Additionally, AI costs may rise in the future, as some companies appear to be losing money currently in order to gain market share. As stated above, these factors will impact future gaps across regions, institutions, etc., though it is unclear what that impact will be due to competing factors.

Discussion: Some resources today are seen as important to provide to all citizens and residents, while others are provided by an institution, and yet others are considered important only in the context of specific projects or activities, or are left for the individual to acquire and use. It is currently unclear where AI services and tools fall. Should they be provided at a national level? An institutional level? A project level? Or should they be left for the individual to acquire as they see fit?

Societal impacts: AI creates a large number of societal challenges: environmental, political, economic, legal, ethical, etc. While these are beyond the research software community, the research software community could choose to speak about them or contribute to addressing them.

4. A call to action

This vision will not realize itself. It requires action across people in multiple groups and with multiple roles, groups that we, the authors, belong to: those who develop research software, those who lead research projects and/or institutions, those who fund research or make policy, and those in the AI and technology community. We call for engagement in several areas:

4.1. For people who develop research software

Strengthen your foundations: The practices that make software reliable – testing, human review, documentation, version control – are your most important tools in the AI era. Continue to invest in them, and advocate for their continued use.

Embrace responsibility: Remember that you are responsible for the software you produce, especially AI-generated components. Your role is to understand what the code does, verify that it works, and own the results. Beyond professional responsibility, emerging legal and regulatory frameworks may increasingly require this.

Value research ethics and integrity: Continue to promote transparency, reproducibility, and rigor in development and use of research software.

Learn: The landscape is evolving rapidly. Stay up to date, by evaluating tools, developing and learning about best practices, and adapting to changing capabilities.

Share what you learn: The research community is navigating this transition together. Document your experiences, contribute to emerging best practices, and help others benefit from your insights.

Protect your data: Understand where data flows when using AI tools, both during their use and when deploying research tools that have relied on AI for their development. Ensure that how data is handled is consistent with data management plans, ethics approvals, and information security requirements.

Use your computational/data resources effectively: This affects both time-to-solution and environmental impact, and is a challenge today. AI could make this worse, if it's not a part of the spec, but AI could also help optimize and improve this if it's considered part of the process.

4.2. For people who lead research projects and/or institutions

Invest in people: AI is not a substitute for human expertise. Sustained investment to both develop and support skilled software practitioners is essential for realizing the benefits of AI-assistance while managing its risks. This starts early: undergraduate education should equip students with a solid foundation in the proper and responsible use of AI tools in research contexts. Educators and trainers need to have a larger role earlier in these discussions, rather than just being expected to adapt to use new technologies after they've been developed. It also

continues through on-the-job learning: there is a risk that AI could erode the apprenticeship pipeline through which people develop the skills needed to verify and maintain research software, as both basic training and practice is needed to develop skills. If people depend on AI without being able to do the equivalent work without out, how do we ensure they know enough to truly validate it.

Create space for learning: The landscape is evolving rapidly. Provide time and resources for all research software engineers and researchers to evaluate tools, develop best practices, and adapt to changing capabilities.

Evaluate where AI adds value: Not all uses of AI in research software are equally productive or appropriate. Stay informed about the evidence for where these tools genuinely improve outcomes and where they may introduce more risk than benefit, and set expectations accordingly.

Set clear expectations: Adapt policies and norms for AI use in research and research software that prioritize quality, transparency, and reproducibility. Make these expectations known and support their implementation, even before updated/new policies are fully in place.

Rethink evaluation: How we assess researchers, RSEs, papers, and software can often reward quantity over quality. AI will amplify outcomes towards whatever we incentivise. Consider what needs to change in hiring, promotion, and peer review to reward rigour, not just output. For people who fund research or make policy

Recognize the stakes: Research software quality is foundational to research quality. Investment in the people, practices, and infrastructure that ensure software reliability is investment in the integrity of research itself.

Support community coordination: Many challenges of AI in research software are collective problems that require collective solutions. Fund the development of shared resources, including updated best practices and training for research software production in the AI era, and community processes, such as the collective development and dissemination of these resources, in order to enable coordinated action at scale.

Take a long view: The AI-assisted tooling landscape will continue to evolve. Support approaches that build lasting capacity and adaptability, not just responses to today's specific tools.

4.3. For people in the AI and technology community

Engage with research values: Research has particular requirements for transparency, reproducibility, validation and verification, and rigor. And research has its own culture. Tools and studies designed for research contexts should reflect these values and culture.

Support attribution and provenance: Make it easier to document and track how AI-assistance was used in producing research artifacts. Support enabling the transparency that research integrity requires.

Proceed thoughtfully: The impacts of AI-assistance on research software are still unfolding. Listen to practitioners, acknowledge limitations, and collaborate on addressing challenges and opportunities as they emerge.

5. Moving forward

This vision is a snapshot of our thinking created at a time of rapid change, and we recognize we do not know exactly what research software production will look like in five or ten years. But we can commit to principles that will guide us regardless:

- Research impact is the goal, but impact must be understood broadly: advancing knowledge, addressing societal challenges, building capacity, and sustaining the people and communities who make research possible. These goals are shaped by human choices, institutional contexts, and the infrastructures we build and maintain.
- Quality cannot be compromised for speed of development.
- Humans must remain responsible for research integrity.
- Transparency enables others to verify and build upon our work.
- Community and collaboration matter. We navigate this transition together.

Discussion: "quality" above has multiple aspects, including rigor, transparency, trustworthiness, accuracy, performance, portability, etc.

Research communities have navigated technological transitions before, such as the introductions of computational science and data science. What matters now, as then, is not the technology itself but the choices we make about how to use it. The pursuit of knowledge remains a human responsibility.

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